

The Impact of Modernism on Islam

Introduction:

Islam and modernity is a topic of discussion in contemporary sociology of religion. The history of Islam chronicles different interpretations and approaches. Historically, Islam has had different schools of thought moving in many directions. Modernity is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon rather than a unified and coherent one. (Abdolkarim Soroush, 2005).

In this essay, I look at the impact of modernism on Islam. Modernism can change attitudes toward religion and have both positive and negative effects on religion. Islam is no exception to this rule. The new age and modern values have led Muslims to take a different approach to their religion and different approaches to modernism. There is an approach to reconciling Islam with modernism supported by Islamic intellectuals. Islamic intellectuals do not see any contradiction between modern values and Islam. They try to reconcile the two through tradition and the sacred text and offer a reading of the text through scientific methods such as hermeneutics that do not contradict modern patterns with Islamic values.

Another approach is the adverse reaction to modernism (Cesari, 2009, 12). This group wants to go back to the past, have a negative attitude towards modernism, and see their Islamic identity in danger. This group can be called Islamic fundamentalism (Bruce, 2008: 39). They oppose anything new and believe that the Islamic tradition does not overlap with modern values. In this essay, I focus on these two groups of Muslims, which are two opposite approaches to modernity and the interpretation of Islam. I will try to discuss the reasons for both sides.

Modernism and Modernity:

There is no single definition of the concept of modernism. There is also disagreement among thinkers about when modernism started in the West. Some observed the date of modernization of society in the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries before industrialization (Davie, 2013: 91). If we consider the origin of modernism in the centralization of empirical science and post-middle age philosophy, this view that modernism began between the 15 and 16 centuries is arguably defensible. The first fathers of experimental and modern science and modern philosophers emerged at this time, such as Newton, Francis Bacon, and Descartes. Suppose

we trace modernism as origins to secularism. The beginning of modernism can be considered after the Treaty of Westphalia at the end of the Thirty Years' War in the seventeenth century. Furthermore, let's consider the origin of modernism as the industrialization of societies, which was itself the result of the progress and development of science (Davie, 2013: 2).

We can consider modernism in the late 18th and early 19th centuries with the invention of the steam engine. However, Grace Davie distinguished between the term modernism and modernity. According to her, modernity has something to do with industrialization, Urbanization and Production. But modernism is a more cultural term, and it can be understood as anti-traditionalism or secularization/secularism and also progress (Davie, 2013: 2, 91-92)

Modernity means what is new and is opposite to the old. It means giving originality to what is modern and new—in other words, preferring a new idea or new method over a traditional and old idea. According to Steve Bruce, part of what we mean by modernization is the fragmentation of social institutions into ever more specialized units and the division of social life into distinct spheres, each with its own values and procedures. In this sense, modernism relates to the secularization of society. Bruce and Davie both meant the clergy dominated many social functions in the Middle Ages. Education, healthcare, welfare, and social values were all had in control by the clergies. However, in the modern era, their all have their own realm dominated by their own expertise, values, and assumption. (Bruce, 2008: 16, 17 & Davie, 2013: 2). Another significant feature of modernism is rationalism as a method that can trace back to the Enlightenment period.

Modernism describes a range of cultural movements rooted in the changes in Western society. It is a stream of thought that means human use of their knowledge, technology, and empirical ability to produce, improve, and change the environment, resulting from Humanism. Rise of modernism can be seen as a reaction against tradition and Christianity from a Theocentric point of view to anthropocentrism. In this view, human is central. Human replaces God and finds himself/herself free and can determine their own destiny, break the taboos of the past, and shape their own life. Friedrich Nietzsche's famous phrase "God is dead" may be considered the doctrine of modernism. Of course, this phrase itself can have different interpretations. For example, Christian morality has no place in modern society, the church no longer has the power it once had, and various other interpretations.

Thus, a modern society shaped Western society; modern society was an industrial and scientific society. Its political form was the "nation-state". In modern society, economic growth has played a dominant and irrevocable role. This society's primary intellectual and

philosophical systems were also rationalism and utilitarianism. From this, it is clear that the emergence of modernity in the Western world dates back to the Renaissance and has gone through stages until it reached its peak in the nineteenth century. Therefore, I think all the above statements about the history of the emergence of modernity can be justified and accepted.

It is worth noting that modernism does not necessarily contradict spirituality and belonging to a particular religion. Because many human beings can consider themselves rational, humanist, interested in experimental science, and secular, and still believe in God and religious values and teachings and consider themselves religious. This is where the impact of modernism on religion, and in this essay on Islam, comes into play.

Islam facing modernism:

The connection between the West and the East has existed since ancient times. The connection between these two worlds has a historical continuous. From Alexander's invasion and the influence of Hellenism on the Eastern world to the Crusades and the impact of Islamic science and the golden civilization of Islam from the 10 to 13 centuries on the West in the Middle Ages, we can find interactions between East and West. In the same way, in the new era, technological, intellectual, scientific, and Western lifestyles have impacted the lives of Muslims. This new approach to the Western world took place through imperialism. When they could not resist firearms and their successive defeats in the wars, the Eastern world made them realize their passivity and think of reviving Islamic thought. In other words, the military power of the West, gained through industrialization, forced the Muslims to reconsider. The Islamic world is now very similar to that of the European Protestant reformation. Referring to the ideas of Iqbal Lahori (1877-1938), Abu al-Ali Maududi (1903-1979), Jamal al-Din al-Afghani (1839-1897), Muhammad Abduh (1849-1905), etc (Cesari, 2009, 12). They were among the first Muslim thinkers to call on Muslims to escape passivity and called for Islamic rationalism, reawakening, and seizing power.

This invitation to escape passivity took two forms. One was the escape from intellectual and philosophical passivity that sought to overlap with modernism and the advancement of thought. This approach is a kind of " Dialogue Among Civilizations" This means that we must use the experiences of the West, and just as they focused on democracy, thought, rationalism, and science, we Muslims must return to the golden age by rethinking our identities. This can be achieved by learning from the West, not by enmity with the West (Cesari, 2009, 17). Another approach was to avoid passivity in the face of Western

modernism, which sought to return to the beginning of Islam and reject all Western values. This approach had an anti-Western approach, a kind of "Clash of Civilization" (Inglehart & Norris, 2011: 135 & Davie, 2013: 225). These two interpretations were opposed to each other's.

Islamic intellectualism (Islamic Modernism):

Religious modernism is not a phenomenon specific to Islam but can be seen in similar situations in other religions. *Islamic modernism* is a movement described as the "Muslim First Ideological Response," which seeks to reconcile Islam with Western values such as nationalism, democracy, civil rights, rationality, equality, and progress. Islamic modernity plays a significant role in conducting a "critical inquiry into traditional conventional concepts and methods of jurisprudence" and a new approach to Islamic theology and interpretation of the Qur'an (Moaddel, 2005: 2). Westernization of many Islamic countries became commonplace and changed the way people thought about social life. The new education system was adapted from the West, and young people were sent to Europe and educated in the universities and became known to the West's new environments. These young people came back to their countries and became intellectuals, philosophers, theologians, and elites who influenced the Westernization of Islamic countries' culture and educational activities. Many modern Islamic thinkers have emerged in Egypt, Iran, Indonesia, Turkey and India over the past century. Not only the reformist groups play a significant role in the revival of Islam, they also helped to build a well-educated Muslim middle class- a group of people, that is, who began to raise questions about a host of characteristically modern concerns, including the status of women, the challenge of pluralism, and the role of morality in market economies (Davie, 2013: 224).

It must be said that the goal of the Islamic Modernists was to make Islam adaptable and responsive to the conditions of advanced societies. Their message was that Muslims could live actively in the modern world, deal with and participate in the modern world and new issues, and at the same time remain faithful to their religion. Muslim modernists thought that Islam had given them this authority and commissioned them to reform and eliminate Muslims' religious, moral degeneration (Quran 4:114). Their thinking was basically based on the Islamic concepts of "renewal" and "reform" in the Quran.

One of the highlights of Islamic modernists that differentiates them from fundamentalists is the scientific methods of reading texts. "They tried to 'understand the spirit or purpose of the Qur'anic teachings, not to cling to its literal meaning without thinking.' Another important

point is that they "re-raised the issue of the relationship between religion and reason and took a rationalist approach to issues." Hence Muhammad Abdu, the Egyptian Islamic modernist, and his movement have sometimes been referred to as "*Neo-Mu'tazilites*"¹. (Akhlagh, 2015: 4). They made a clear connection between Qur'anic thought and modern thought on some essential points. That is why modern values such as democracy, human rights, and pluralism have never been seen as in conflict with Islam. They had the ability to accept values and standards outside the Qur'an and Sunnah, which often originated in non-Muslim cultures. They argued that acceptable values that these values do not contradict with values of Islam and even reflect the true values of Islam.

Their aim is not just to copy the West but to revive the spirit of Islam and believe that Islam has no conflict with human rights, pluralism, tolerance and women's rights. Today we have Muslim feminists who, with a hermeneutic view of the age of the Prophet of Islam and the reforms that the prophet made for women in the 7th century in his time, believe that we should follow in Muhammad's footsteps. Muhammad did not make the conditions ideal for women but reformed the situation for women according to his time, and this reform is considered the tradition of Muhammad. For example, in pre-Islamic Saudi Arabia, girls were buried alive in some tribes, and Muhammad violated this pre-Islamic tradition. Before Islam, women never inherited, but Muhammad made some rules that women should inherit, which meant reforms in favor of women. Consequently, with a historical understanding, one can rationally analyze all different subjects in this way and know the spirit of Islam.

Another example, the arguments that jihad in the Qur'an, has made Islam a religion of violence in the eye of many people, are also incorrect in the historical reading of Islamic intellectuals. From a historical point of view, we see that Muhammad and his companions were in the absolute minority. They were a religious minority who were persecuted. The concept of jihad is all self-defense and is a kind of the *just-war* to save one group's life and not attack war; how can a minority group of 200 people attack the power of *Quraish*, who governed Arabia at that time and had military and wealth! Therefore, Jihad should understand in the context of a situation and historical background, and it's not about going to war against innocent people in the west and acts of terror! However, the prophet's worldview on human

¹ Mu'tazila is an Islamic group that appeared in early Islāmic history and it developed an Islamic type of rationalism, partly influenced by Ancient Greek philosophy. The Mu'tazila are Islamic rationalists, in their belief that religious understandings are accessible to man by means of his intelligence and reason. Mu'tazilites believe that good and evil are not always determined by revealed scripture or interpretation of scripture, but they are rational categories that could be "established through unaided reason" (Fakhri, 1983: 47)

life and human value and dignity is mentioned in the Qur'an, which is also found in the Talmud²:

"whoever killed a soul...it should be considered as though he had killed all mankind; and that whoever saved a soul should be regarded as though he had saved all mankind." (Quran 5:32).

Islamic Fundamentalism (Salafism):

The second approach can be called Islamic fundamentalism. Fundamentalism is itself a product of modernity, in so far as they are born out of the clash between modernity and traditional cultures (Davie, 2013: 190). Fundamentalism is at one hand an anti-modern utopia and, on other hand, a modern social movement (Davie, 2013: 193). This movement also has a new reading and originated in the modern era and can be traced in the works of Sayyid Qutb (1906-1966), Hassan al-Banna (1906-1949) and Abul a'la Maududi (1903-1979), Egyptians and Pakistanian scholars of Islam which they work had a direct influence on Talibanism. Moreover, we can name Wahabism, which is rooted in Muhammad Abd al-Wahhab (1703-1792) Islamic scholar of Saudi Arabia. The terms: Islamic Fundamentalism, Islamism, Salafism, Wahabism, Islamic Extremism can sometimes be interchangeable and have the same root and meaning by minor differences, which I am not going on these details in this essay. The Islamic revolution in Iran (1979) is an example case of Islamic fundamentalist movement in 20 centuries (Davie, 2013: 194).

Everything new and modern from the West is dangerous for them, and it must be confronted. According to them, Western culture is a threat to Islam and the United States is the main promoter of Western culture (Bruce, 2008: 3). They oppose any kind of pluralism, tolerance, and open-mindedness. They have a negative attitude to the autonomy of the individual and the sovereignty of reason (Davie, 2013: 194). What matters is a return to the past³. In other words, fundamentalism is a world view that highlights specific essential "truths" of traditional faiths and applies them with earnestness and fervor to twentieth-century realities (Davie, 2013: 188). Modernity, in their view, is the breaking of the transcendental principles, that is, the immutable and eternal principles that govern everything, and man becomes aware of them through revelation and inspiration. In this sense, modernism is opposed to religion.

² "Whoever destroys a soul, it is considered as if he destroyed an entire world. And whoever saves a life, it is considered as if he saved an entire world". (Mishnah Sanhedrin 4:5; *Yerushalmi Talmud* 4:9)

³ It should be noted that their view of the past is not based on hermeneutics and correct reading of history, and they suffer from anachronism.

What is happening now in some parts of the Islamic world is completely anti-modern and is against its positive achievements. Freedom, democracy, individualism and citizenship rights, women's rights, the rights of ethnic and religious minorities, tolerance and equality, are positive categories of the modern world that are either ignored or attacked in the Islamic world by fundamentalists in many cases. In recent decades, especially in the Middle East, these issues have been addressed, intensifying in recent years. They use modern tools such as weapons, radio, television, etc., but consider themselves the enemy of modernism (Davie, 2013: 190). The image they created of Islam is a violent Islam with the keyword jihad in their own eyes and terrorism in the eyes of the West. They consider anyone who opposes them an infidel and a traitor (Bruce, 2008: 8).

As Steve Bruce wrote in His book, fundamentalism has become a term of abuse, suggesting a lack of intellectual maturity, and they look at the holy text without error and have a literal reading of text without any sense of analyzing the context (Bruce, 2008: 12). In my opinion, the only thing they understand from religion is a series of primitive unchangeable jurisprudential rules, and there is no spirituality or self-knowledge in their understanding of religion. They are anti-thought, anti-philosophy, anti-mysticism, anti-beauty, and anti-wisdom. They have only a superficial and limited interpretation of religious texts, resulting in ignorance of understanding scientific methods. Most of them have never been educated in Academia, resulting from anti-Western prejudices. Another important feature of fundamentalism is "us and them" mentality that emerges supplies a further characteristic of fundamentalism (Davie, 2013: 190).

Fundamentalists do not believe in the evolution of history. They see the end of history 1400 years ago when the Prophet of Islam did everything man needed to do. Hence the end of history 1400 years ago for fundamentalists. Their view of the Qur'an is the maximum view, which means that in the Qur'an and Sunnah, everything that human beings need is included. Islamic modernists, on the other hand, have a minimalist view of the Qur'an and Sunnah, meaning that the least human cognitive needs arise in religion and history, and we can discover more truths about Islam over time and rationalize the signs of God every day. In other words, divine revelation has not been once and for all but is a fluid thing in history. When the fundamentalists considered 1400 years ago to be the end of history, the way of reasoning, thinking, progress, and movement is closed. In such an attitude, there is a stagnation of thought, in which any creativity and innovation is condemned.

Conclusion:

In this short essay, we tried to show the impact of modernism on Islam. We first define the concept of modernism and show that modernism is a Western phenomenon that has penetrated from the West to the East and has directly impacted Muslims. A group sought to reconcile their religion with modern values, believing that the spirit of Islam was not in conflict with humanistic and rationalist values. The other group saw modernism as a serious threat to their identity, ethnicity, and religion. It called for a return to early Islam and opposed modern values.

The difference between modernists and fundamentalists is in the way they look at the Qur'an and Sunnah. Both called themselves Muslims, but their understanding of Islam was quite different. The former seeks and finds all modern values in Islam itself. The latter rejects all modern values and sees them as contrary to Islam. The former beliefs in pluralism, democracy, human rights, ethics, science, progress and development, and the latter oppose these principles and values that define the basis of modernism.

In the end, I must say that these two forms of attitude toward religion in the face of modernism are present in all religions, and we also have Christian, Jewish, Buddhist, and Hindu fundamentalism. We also have Christian, Jewish, Buddhist, and Hindu liberals. It seems that facing modernism in all religions has created these two attitudes, which itself is necessary for another article.

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